

INFLUENCE OF HIGH STRAIN RATE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF AL-STEEL FIBRES COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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The effect of strain rate on mechanical properties of the composite materials consisting of aluminium matrix reinforced with different volume fractions of different strength steel fibres was investigated.

The specimens used were in form of cubes with 5 mm edge length and were loaded in the fibre axis direction.

The compressive loading was performed at quasi-static rates $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ using the Instron equipment and at high strain rates $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ using the system of split Hopkinson's bar.

In the work the effects of matrix, fibre volume fractions, their strength and strain rate on the course of $\sigma - \epsilon$ curves were compared.

Increase of the strain rate by 5 orders results in increase of the nominal stress of matrix and also of the reinforcing fibres. Stress increase in the composite material is a significant function of the volume fraction and strength of the fibres. The results of work have indicated the possibility to utilize the rule of mixture in these materials when loaded also at high strain rates.

Practical application of the composite materials in many cases requires knowledge of their mechanical properties at high loading rates. The effect of high strain rate in the classical materials was sufficiently investigated lately [1-5], whereas only few works [6,7] have dealt with that problem in the composite materials.

The aim of our contribution was to study the effect of high strain rate on the mechanical properties of composite material based on the Al Cu₄ Mg₂ Mn alloy reinforced with two types of steel fibres with different strength.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTS

The composite material was prepared by the vacuum hot pressing technology. The reinforcing component were the steel fibres of maraging type, while their tensile strength was 3.5 GPa in the first case and 2.2 GPa in the other case; 210 GPa Young's modulus and ~ 2 % ductility. The matrix was of non-hardened dural alloy. Study of mechanical properties was performed with the composite material reinforced with 9 and 17 volume per cents of steel fibres 150 μ m in diameter. The specimens used were prepared in the form of cubes 5 mm in edge length. The properties were studied in the fibre axis direction.

The quasi-static compression tests were carried out on the Instron equipment and the dynamic tests on the equipment of split Hopkinson's bar with loading bars 8 mm in dia. [8]. The bars were of maraging steel. The experiments were performed at room temperature. The attained strain rates at the quasi-static experiments were $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and at the dynamical tests $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. During the experiments planarity of loading faces of the specimens was maintained and the abutting surfaces were lubricated.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the statical tests the strain was measured with the use of an extensometer with 500:1 amplification. In the statical and also in the dynamical tests the nominal values of stress and strain were evaluated. The statical hardening curves of the matrix and also of the composite materials, reinforced with 9 and 17 volume per cents of steel fibres with two different strength values are shown in

Fig. 1. A pronounced effect of fibre volume fraction and strength on the resulting properties of the composite material is clearly seen.

Fig. 1 Dependence of nominal stress on the nominal strain at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Curve 1 - matrix, curves 3 and 5 - composite material with the fibres of higher strength, reinforced with 9 and/or 17 volume per cents of steel fibres. Curves 2 and 4 - composite material with the fibres of lower strength reinforced with 9 and/or 17 volume per cents of fibres.

The dynamic curves of hardening of the same materials are shown in Fig. 2. Shape of dynamic curves of hardening is similar to the static ones, with that difference only that the nominal stresses are shifted towards higher values.

Range of the strain rates in our experiments falls yet within the extent, where approximately linear increase of the stress, depending on the strain rate can be considered. Because the evaluation was performed at the low strains /max. 2%/ the temperature increase at the high strain rates was neglected, as it was unimportantly low in our case [5]. As it follows from the hardening curves shown in

Figs. 1 and 2 the matrix and the composite materials are sensitive to the strain rate. In order to assess this sensitivity quantitatively, the nominal stresses for 1, 1.5 and 2 % strain, at the both strain rates were plotted in Fig. 3. The sensitivity of materials to the strain rate is expressed by the slope of linear dependences in this figure.

Fig. 2 Dependence of nominal stress on the nominal strain at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Designation of the curves is the same as in Fig. 1.

From the courses of linear dependences it is seen that the sensitivity of both composite material types to the strain rate is higher than the sensitivity of the matrix. Increase of matrix stress necessary to produce strain of 1 % was 50 MPa at the strain rate increase by 5 orders. At the same strain the increase of necessary stress in the composite material, reinforced with 9 vol. % of fibres with higher strength was 75 MPa or 64 MPa resp. in the material reinforced with the fibres of lower strength. In the case of composite material reinforced with 17 vol.% of fibres with higher strength the increase was 108 MPa or 89 MPa resp. in those reinforced with lower strength fibres. Now it can be concluded that the strength increase is a significant function of the volume fraction of reinforcing fibres.

In evaluation of resulting properties of the composite material it is necessary to start with the properties of its components.

Fig. 3 Dependence of nominal stress on the log. strain rate. Left side; lines 1-3 - matrix, lines 4-6 - composite material with 9 vol. %, lines 7-9 - composite material, 17 vol. % - valid for the fibres of higher strength. Right side: lines 4-6 - composite material with 9 vol. %, lines 7-9 - composite material with 17 vol. % - valid for the fibres of lower strength.

Previous works have proved that the aluminium alloys and steels had the strain hardening coefficient almost independent on the strain rate [9,10]. As seen in Fig. 3 the increase of necessary stress at increase of the strain rate by 5 orders and strains of 1, 1,5 and 2 % is the same, i. e. 50 MPa and it is in a good agreement with the results of works [1,9]. Thus, correctness of values obtained in our measurements has been proved. From the linear dependences of the nominal stresses on the fibre volume fraction the dynamical properties of the fibres used in our experiments were calculated, whereas this dependence is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Dependence of nominal stress on the volume fraction of fibres at 1 % strain. Line 1 - $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, line 2 - $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^3 \text{s}^{-1}$, both for the fibres of lower strength. Line 3 - $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, line 4 - $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^3 \text{s}^{-1}$, both for the fibres of higher strength.

In the figure shown, the appropriate measured nominal stresses for 1 % strain are plotted. From the linear course of nominal stress /at constant strain/ in dependence on the volume % of fibres the possibility to use the rule of mixture is offered. Through application of this rule the increase of nominal stresses of the reinforcing fibres in dependence on the strain rate was calculated. The calculated stress increase in the fibres of higher strength was 350 MPa and in those of lower strength it was 250 MPa. These calculated values are in agreement with work [11].

When using the rule of mixture for 1 % strain the increase of nominal stress at the transition from the quasi-static to the high strain rate was calculated. These values, together with those measured are given in the table.

Tab. 1

Fibre strength [GPa]		3.5		2.2	
Vol. fraction of fibres [%]		9	17	9	17
Stress increase [MPa]	theoretical	77	101	68	84
	measured	75	108	64	89
Matrix stress increase [MPa]		50			

From the analysis of the values given in Tab. 1 a good agreement between the theoretical and measured values of the nominal stress increase, in the given strain rate range is shown. The increase of reinforcing fibre stress is by 7 or 5 times resp. higher, than that of the matrix, and due this fact the increase of the composite material stress is a significant function of volume fraction and strength of the fibres.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of strain rate at $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 10^3s^{-1} in the composite materials of Al Cu4 Mg2 Mn - steel fibres type in dependence on the volume fraction of fibres /9 and 17 vol. %/ of two strength values, namely 3.5 and 2.2 GPa resp./ at room temperature was studied.

The results are as follows:

1. The shape of $\sigma - \epsilon$ curves measured at the given strain rates is the same. Increase of the strain rate results in the shift of the curve towards the higher stress values.
2. At the strain rate increase by 5 orders the nominal stress increase of the matrix, at 1 % strain, attains 50 MPa. The calculated stress increase in the reinforcing fibres of different strength, under the same conditions, is higher by 5 or 7 times respectively.
3. The increase of composite material stress is a significant function of volume fraction and strength of the fibres.
4. A good agreement between the calculated and measured values of the nominal stress in the composite materials offers possibility to apply the rule of mixture also for the materials strained under high rates.

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